
A review on pharmaceutical uses of sea buckthorn

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Abstract: -

Sea-buckthorn (*Hippophaë rhamnoides* L.) pulp oil (SBPO) is a highly valued source of bioactive components, such as fatty acids, phytosterols, tocopherols, carotenoids, and flavonoids. Its diverse properties have made it popular in the cosmetic, food, and medical industries. However, its potential is hindered by challenges like poor water solubility and chemical instability. To address these issues, colloidal vesicle systems are emerging as a vital solution for enhancing its effectiveness and application. The project focused on enhancing the health benefits of oil. To achieve this, we aimed to encapsulate sea-buckthorn oil within a bile salt-based system and evaluate its physicochemical properties. The process of nanobilosomal encapsulation was performed using varying concentrations of the oil, employing thin lipid film hydration followed by ultrasonic homogenization techniques.

Keywords:

Sea-buckthorn pulp, oil, fatty acids, bilisomes, cosmetic.
